

Chemical investigation of the plant resulted in the isolation of a triterpene acid which is characterised as tormentic acid from the following chemical and spectral analyses.

The triterpene acid is isolated as its methyl ester from the acid fraction of the ethanolic extract of the air dried powdered leaves of the plant by column chromatography over neutral alumina using benzene as eluent. The methyl ester, $C_{31}H_{50}O_6$, M^+ 502, mp. 156° , $[\alpha]_D^{25} 43^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$) gives positive Libermann Burchardt test for triterpene. ν_{max}^{nujol} 3500 (OH), 1720 (COOR) cm^{-1} . The PMR spectrum (90MHz, $CDCl_3$) shows signals at 5.3 (m, 1H), 3.63 (s, 3H), 3.02 (d, 1H, $J=10Hz$), 2.90 (m, 1H), 0.78–1.85 ppm (m, 21H).

Treatment of the methyl ester with acetic anhydride and pyridine on steam bath for 6 hours furnishes a diacetyl derivative, $C_{35}H_{54}O_7$, M^+ 586, mp. $101-2^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D^{25} 5^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), ν_{max}^{nujol} 3500 (OH), 1730, 1250 (OCOOR) cm^{-1} . PMR spectrum shows signals at 5.30 (m, 1H), 5.05 (q, 1H, $J_1=5Hz$, $J_2=5Hz$), 4.76 (d, 1H, $J=10Hz$), 2.06 (s, 3H), 1.96 ppm (s, 3H).

Alkaline hydrolysis of the methyl ester gives the free triterpene acid, $C_{30}H_{48}O_6$, mp. $272-3^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -20^\circ$ (pyridine) crystallises from ethanolic chloroform in fine needles.

All these physical and spectral data are found to be in close conformity with tormentic acid previously isolated from *Potentilla tormentilla* Neck (*Rosaceae*)². Complete identity of our triterpene acid as methyl ester with methyl tormentate is established by the direct comparison with an authentic sample (mmp, tlc).

This work, probably in our knowledge, constitute the second isolation of tormentic acid.

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Studies on the Synthesis of Heterocyclic Compounds—Part-I. 1-Hydroxy-3-Substituted-4-Keto-3,4-Dihydrophthalazines

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1-HYDROXY-3-phenyl-4-keto-3,4-dihydrophthalazine is useful in the chemotherapy of tuberculosis¹. The following general methods are known for the preparation of the title compounds²⁻⁶.

(i) Isomerisation of N-arylamino-phthalimide by alcoholic sodium ethoxide.

(ii) Oxidation of 1-hydroxy-3-aryl-3,4-dihydrophthalazine-4-acetic acid by potassium permanganate.

(iii) Demethylation of *o*-methyl ethers of 1-hydroxy-3-aryl-4-keto-3,4-dihydrophthalazines by hydrobromic acid.

The present communication describes a new method for the synthesis of hydroxyphthalazines using polyphosphoric acid (PPA) as a condensing agent. This method has the advantage over other methods in respect of high yields with clean products.

Experimental

Synthesis of 1-hydroxy-3-substituted-4-keto-3,4-dihydrophthalazines :

A mixture of phthalic anhydride (0.03M) and mono N-substituted hydrazine (0.03M) was heated on a sandbath with PPA (12 ml : 20 gm : : H_3PO_4 : P_2O_5) at $150^\circ(\pm 10^\circ)$ for half an hour and allowed to cool. The mass was decomposed with ice-water and the compound purified by crystallisation from acetic acid.

TABLE

No.	R	Yield	M.P. °C	Colour	References
1	H	80%	333°	Colourless	2-4
2	C_6H_5	78%	211°	Yellowish-white	5,6
3	$C_6H_4(NO_2)$, (2 : 4)	92%	271°	Yellowish-white	7
4	$CH_2C_6H_4$	68%	245°	Yellowish-white	8

The compounds are soluble in dilute alkali giving red colouration and insoluble in dilute mineral acid. Further work along this line is in progress.

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Study of Some Reactions on Acetophenone Derivatives II

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IN continuation of our previous work¹ some reactions on acetophenone derivatives (5-chloro-2-hydroxy acetophenone)² have been studied.

The oxime of 5-chloro-2-hydroxy acetophenone when treated with phosphorus oxychloride gave an acetanilide derivative which on hydrolysis with dilute sulphuric acid gave the known amino derivative³.

5-Chloro-2-hydroxy acetophenone when treated with benzoic anhydride and sodium benzoate at 190° for 10 hr gave 3-benzoyl derivative which on alkaline hydrolysis led to the known 6-chloro-flavone⁴. Similarly when heated with acetic

anhydride and fused sodium acetate at 190° for 10 hr it gave the product to which 3-acetyl-6-chloro-2-methylchromone structure was assigned. The above product on hydrolysis shows the characteristic peaks for chromone⁵ at 1650; 1600; 1776; 1378 cm⁻¹. The characteristic peaks for coumarin at 1737 for δ -lactone and 1668 cm⁻¹ for (-C=C-CO-) were absent. 5-Chloro-2-hydroxy acetophenone on condensation with benzaldehyde in the presence of ethanolic potassium hydroxide gave chalkone. It showed yellow colouration to the Wilson test⁶ and isomerised to 6-chloroflavone when the ethanolic solution was refluxed with phosphoric acid for 12 hr.

5-Chloro-2-hydroxy acetophenone on heating with ethyl acetoacetate at 130° for 1½ hr in the presence of 80% sulphuric acid gave the product to which 8-acetyl-6-chloro-4-methyl coumarin structure was assigned on the basis of IR data (the characteristic peaks for coumarin at 1737 for δ -lactone and 1668 cm⁻¹ for (-C=C-CO-)).

Experimental

Oxime of 5-chloro-2-hydroxy acetophenone(I), acetanilide derivative(II), 2-amino-4-chlorophenol(III); 3-benzoylflavone(IV); 6-chloroflavone(V); 3-acetyl-6-chloro-2-methyl chromone(VI), 6-chloro-2-methyl chromone(VII), chalkone derivative(VIII) and 8-chloroflavanone(IX) were prepared according to the procedure described¹ (Table 1).

8-Acetyl-6-chloro-4-methyl coumarin(X) was prepared by heating a mixture of 5-chloro-2-hydroxy acetophenone (3.2 g) and ethyl acetoacetate (3 ml) in the presence of 80% sulphuric acid (10 ml) on oil bath at 130° for 1½ hr. The reaction mixture was left overnight, poured over crushed ice, the solid product separated was crystallised from ethyl acetate and petroleum ether (40-60°) in white needles.

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF CHEMICAL COMPOUNDS

Nos.	Molecular Formula	M.P.* °C	Yield %	Physical Property	Analysis percentage							
					C		H		Cl		N	
					Found	Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found	Cal.
I	C ₈ H ₉ O ₂ ClN	180	60	White needles	52.3	51.75	4.8	4.3	19.17	19.14	7.5	7.54
II	C ₈ H ₉ O ₂ ClN	183	35	Pale brown needles	52.0	51.75	4.7	4.31	18.7	19.14	7.5	7.54
III	C ₈ H ₈ OClN	138	50	Brown shining plates	50.28	50.13	4.31	4.18	24.44	24.74	9.97	9.57
IV	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl	190	50	White needles	73.0	73.33	3.47	3.61	10.2	9.86	—	—
V	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₂ Cl	172	50	Yellow needles	70.5	70.17	4.4	3.58	13.28	13.84	—	—
VI	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₂ Cl	134	60	White	60.3	61.06	4.3	3.8	15.34	15.01	—	—
VII	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₂ Cl	147	30	White	61.58	61.69	3.4	3.59	18.51	18.25	—	—
VIII	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl	112	50	Yellow	69.6	69.65	4.25	4.09	14.6	13.73	—	—
IX	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl	183	60	White	69.6	69.65	4.25	4.09	13.28	13.73	—	—
X	C ₁₇ H ₉ O ₂ Cl	184	38	White	61.23	61.06	3.96	3.8	15.54	15.01	—	—

* All the mps are uncorrected.

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